

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

WORLD EXPERIENCE IN INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES

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МИРОВОЙ ОПЫТ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ АКЦИОНЕРНЫХ ОБЩЕСТВ

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Abstract

The article discusses the issue of global experience in increasing the competitiveness of joint-stock companies, stimulating the internal development of joint-stock companies. As you know, one of the most important problems of enterprises, including those based on equity capital, is achieving a certain level of competitiveness, which affects the state of the world market. International experience has been analyzed in order to increase the competitiveness of the domestic market in terms of reducing the negative consequences of globalization processes.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается вопрос о мировом опыте повышения конкурентоспособности акционерных обществ, стимулирующий внутреннему развитию акционерных обществ. Как известно, одной из важнейших проблем предприятий, в том числе базирующихся на акционерном капитале, выступает достижение определенного уровня конкурентоспособности, влияющий на состояние мирового рынка. Проанализирован международный опыт с целью повышению конкурентоспособности отечественного рынка с точки зрения уменьшения негативных последствий процессов глобализации.

Keywords: competitiveness, joint stock company, competitiveness factors, innovation, competitiveness index.

Ключевые слова: конкурентоспособность, акционерное общество, факторы конкурентоспособности, инновации, индекс конкурентоспособности.

Introduction. Each country has its own characteristics of the functioning of joint-stock companies, but it cannot be said that the problems of the functioning of joint-stock companies are of a local nature. At the present stage of economic development, associated with globalization and internationalization processes, when world economic ties go beyond countries and continents, the most significant criterion for the demand for products and production efficiency is competitiveness, the increase of which means a transition to an intensive type of expanded reproduction, allowing for business sustainability. Creating competitive advantages over rivals becomes a strategic direction of activity of the state and its bodies in the field of ensuring the competitiveness of the national economy. At the same time, increasing competitiveness concerns all levels of its hierarchy: products, enterprises, industries, regions and the country as a whole, but the competitiveness of an enterprise as the main link of the economy is of particular importance.

Theoretical aspects of the research. With insufficient competition, dominant firms can use their market power to charge higher prices, offer lower quality,

and block potential competitors from entering the market, meaning that entrepreneurs and small businesses cannot participate on a level playing field and new ideas cannot become new goods and services. Research also links market power to inequality. In an economy without adequate competition, prices and corporate profits rise while worker wages fall. This means that large corporations and their shareholders gain wealth while consumers and workers' pay the costs.

In early theories, the main attention was paid to the study of the comparative advantages of countries, which are based on differences in the endowment of countries with production factors and, as a consequence, differences in relative costs, which were reflected in the works of A. Smith, D. Ricardo, Heckscher-Ohlin³.

The highest level of implementation of scientific and technological progress in production is the increasing role of human capital in creating competitive advantages, when the key factor, along with capital and labor in its classical sense, becomes knowledge embodied in highly qualified workers.

³Smith A. An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations. Books 1-3. M.: Direct-Media. 2014. - 442 p. Ricardo D. The beginnings of political economy and tax-

tion. M.: 2016. - 234 p. Say J.B. Treatise on Political Economy. Frederic Bastiat Economic sophisms. Economic harmonies - M.: Delo, 2000. - 232 p.

The foundations of the theory of comparative advantage were laid by A. Smith and D. Ricardo; they explored the country's ability to participate in international trade in conditions of free competition. Based on their research, subsequent theories developed that either expanded the analysis proposed by A. Smith and

D. Ricardo, or refuted their theory, thereby highlighting new aspects in the development of competitive advantages as a more progressive form of comparative advantage. (Table 1).

Table 1

Main stages in the development of the theory of competitive advantage⁴

No.	Development stage	Sources of Advantage	Followers of the theory
1.	Comparative cost advantage	Availability of cheap production resources	A. Smith, D. Ricardo, O. Heckscher, B. Ohlin
2.	Competitive advantage through innovation	Scientific and technological progress and its implementation in new technologies and methods of organizing production	M. Posner, R. Vernon, P. Krugman, G. Hufbauer;
3.	Competitive advantage based on investment	Intra-industry and inter-industry trade based on economies of scale	S. Lindert, K. Lancaster, Grubel and Lloyd
4.	Knowledge-based competitive advantage	Human capital as a leading factor of production	R. Findlay, G. Kierzkowski, D. Kesting, A. Anderson
5.	Systemic competitive advantages	Factors of production, demand parameters, strategy, presence of related and supporting industries	M. Porter

The influence of knowledge and qualifications of employees on the process of creating competitive advantages was studied in their works by D. Kesting, G. Kierzkowski, A. Anderson. As the world economy develops and the achievements of scientific and technological progress spread, what began to come to the fore is not the comparative advantages endowed with the country's economy as a whole, but the competitive advantages that are created by each individual company, due to the fact that it is the companies that represent countries in the world market.

The final stage in the evolution of comparative advantages is M. Porter's systemic competitive advantages. Unlike other researchers, M. Porter analyzed not individual factors that determine the creation of competitive advantages, but the interaction of factors, which is reflected in the national diamond system.

In accordance with the ideas of M. Porter, factors characterizing the competitiveness of an enterprise can be classified as follows:

Table 2

Classification of competitiveness factors according to M. Porter⁵

No.	Factors	Essence of factors
1.	According to the development	<i>Main Factors</i> - these are natural resources, climatic conditions, personnel qualifications, etc.
		<i>Developed Factors</i> - this is a modern infrastructure for information exchange in the enterprise, highly qualified personnel and research departments
2.	By level of specialization	<i>Specialized Factors</i> - this is the specialization of personnel, infrastructure, the availability and development of databases at the enterprise, etc.
		<i>General factors</i> are among those that occur frequently and, accordingly, provide the enterprise with limited competitive advantages
3.	By area of creation	<i>Natural factors</i> include geographical location, natural resources, etc.
		<i>Artificially created factors</i> - these are higher order factors that provide more sustainable and high competitiveness

The life cycle of competitive advantage according to M. Porter consists of three phases:

⁴Compiled by the author. Source: Benderskaya E.A. Stages of the evolution of competitive advantages // Electronic scientific publication "Scientific Notes of Tomsk State University" 2014, Volume 5, No. 4, pp. 1201-1205 https://pnu.edu.ru/media/ejournal/articles-2014/TGU_5_343.pdf

⁵Systematized by the author. Source: Porter M. International competition: Competitive advantages of countries. Per. from English edited by Shchetinina V.D. // M. International relations, 1993. 896 p.

Pic. 2. Life cycle of competitive advantage according to M. Porter⁶

The formation of competitive advantages is the first stage of the life cycle and is associated with the constant search for new and qualitative improvement of existing sources of competitive advantages, with the replacement of low-ranking sources of advantages with higher ones, with the search for ways to improve the company's activities as a whole.

The second stage of the vitality of a company's competitive advantages is associated with increasing the efficiency of enterprise management mechanisms,

government support, characteristic features of the national economy, etc.

The third stage of vitality implies destruction and loss of advantage, which can be avoided with the effective use of innovative potential, abandonment of outdated competitive advantages in order to obtain an advantage of a higher rank, etc. The most important reasons for the destruction or loss of competitive advantages M. Porter included:

Pic. 3. Main reasons for the loss of competitiveness advantages according to M. Porter⁷

Competitive advantages can take many forms depending on the specifics of the industry, product and market. When defining competitive advantages, it is important to focus on the needs of consumers and make sure that these advantages are perceived by them as such. The main requirement is that the difference must be real, expressive and significant. B.Karlof notes that "unfortunately, it is too easy to claim that you have competitive advantages without taking the time to check whether these supposed advantages correspond to customer needs. As a result, products with fictitious advantages appear."⁸

Professor R.A.Fatkhutdinov in his works, he revised certain aspects of M. Porter's theory of competitiveness, calling into question the latter's assertion that

"competitiveness is determined by efficiency." In his opinion, the situation is rather the opposite: "the creation and sale of competitive goods allows you to increase profits and improve production efficiency"⁹. N.Z.Safiullin and co-authors define competitiveness as "the possession of properties that create advantages for the subject of economic competition", proposing to consider it in two interrelated planes - factorial and resultant. In addition, in their work they present a classification of competitiveness depending on the object, dividing it into micro-, meso- and macro-competitiveness¹⁰. Modern foreign authors classify competitive advantages as follows:

Table 3

Classification of competitive advantages¹¹

No.	Classification sign	Types of competitive advantages
1.	Depending on condition	Potential and real
2.	Depending on the duration of the benefit	Strategic and tactical
3.	Depending on the source	Advantages of high and low rank

⁶Systematized by the author. Source: *ibid.*

⁷Systematized by the author. Source: Porter M. International competition: Competitive advantages of countries. Per. from English edited by Shchetinina V.D. // M. International relations, 1993. 896 p.

⁸Karlof B. Business strategy [Text]: concept, content, symbols: trans. from English / B. Karlof; ed. E. V. Vinogradova. M.: Economics, 1991. 239 p.

⁹Fatkhutdinov R.A. The essence of competitiveness // Modern competition. 2009. No. 3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/>

¹⁰Safiullin N.Z., Safiullin L.N. Managing the competitiveness of enterprises // Monograph. - Kazan: Publishing house Kazansk. University, 2008. - 189 p.

¹¹Built by the author. Source: Shvets I.Yu. Classification of competitive advantages and factors of various objects // Economics and Management No. 4 - 2011 <http://kafmen.ru/>

The advantages of a high rank include the company having a good reputation, qualified personnel, patents, characterized by long-term R&D, marketing development, modern management, long-term relationships with customers, etc. Thus, the competitiveness of companies, including joint-stock companies, is one of the determining factors in the activity of an enterprise. Competitive advantages are realized, as a rule, at the level of business units and form the basis of business strategy; they are based on unique factors expressed in the ability to transform taking into account changing consumer demands, national and global situations.

Methodological aspects of the research. There are a number of methods generally accepted by the international community for determining the level of competitiveness of an enterprise. Among them, there is a group of formalized methods - matrix methods, methods based on assessing the competitiveness of products manufactured by an enterprise, based on the theory of effective competition, expert and, finally, methods that claim to be called comprehensive, in which attempts are made to maximize the results and prospects of the enterprise's activities. In addition to formalized methods, methods based on the opinions of specialists, the so-called expert methods, have become widespread. A common disadvantage of the latter is the subjectivist approach to assessment, and therefore it is advisable to use precise and expert methods in combination. The experience of developed foreign countries shows that the production of competitive products is the basis for the growth of the country's export and innovation potential.

Foreign experience of the research. Healthy market competition is fundamental to a well-function-

ing U.S. economy. Basic economic theory demonstrates that when firms have to compete for customers, it results in lower prices, better goods and services, more variety, and more innovation. That's why the US government signed the Executive Order on Promoting Competition in the American Economy, which launches a national effort to combat the growing market power in the American economy, seeking to ensure the competitiveness of markets. Although competition is fundamental to a prosperous and fair economy, there is growing evidence that markets across the United States have become less competitive over time and that market power is expanding. There are two types of evidence indicating that concentration problems are widespread in the US economy. First, there is evidence that market concentration, as well as profits and markups, are rising across all industries. Second, market-specific studies show that consolidation has led to harmful price increases, one of the clearest indicators of increased market power.

While informative, industry-wide studies at the national level provide little information about whether increased concentration and markups are the result of reduced competition; that is, they cannot tell us whether concentration is problematic for the US economy. Likewise, increases in markups may result from improvements in technology that reduce marginal costs. On the other hand, increased concentration could also result from anticompetitive mergers or increased barriers to entry, which could also lead to higher markups. In assessing the US experience characterizing government activities related to supporting the processes of increasing the competitiveness of business entities, attention should be paid to a number of important points (pic.4).

Pic. 4. The main areas of activity of the US government to improve the competitiveness of companies¹²

Due to the fact that in recent years there has been widespread penetration of goods and services from Chinese manufacturers into the world market, the experience of the People's Republic of China in increasing

the competitiveness of enterprises deserves special attention. The following main characteristics of the state's management activities aimed at increasing competitiveness should be highlighted:

¹²Systematized by the author. Source: Risin S.I. Foreign experience of state management in increasing the competitiveness of the region // Modern competition. 2009. No. 2. URL:<https://cyberleninka.ru/>

Pic. 5. Measures to improve the competitiveness of enterprises in China¹³

According to the Japanese National Institute of Science and Technology Policy, on average, only 5% of companies use university developments and technologies. Currently, interaction between university science and companies is most often carried out in the form of joint projects, which in itself is also an effective form of using the scientific potential of universities and, from an organizational point of view, represents "horizontal cooperation at the pre-competitive stage"¹⁴. However, the problem, according to Japanese experts, is the need to create a mechanism for transferring the results of research conducted in the universities themselves into the real economy.

In matters of increasing competitiveness at the micro- and macro-level, the experience of the European

Union as a world technological leader is interesting. The EU differs from other countries and their associations in its rather pronounced and increasing emphasis on sustainable environmental development, as well as in the fact that it places special emphasis on innovation as a source of social welfare and transformation of society as a whole. In the long term, increased competitiveness of the economy based on increased labor productivity and improved environmental conditions are linked to an increase in the level and quality of life of EU citizens.

The main areas of the Lisbon strategy for increasing the competitiveness of the economy, on which, according to EU leaders, it was necessary to focus efforts to improve the competitive position of the union, are:

Pic. 6. Main directions of the Lisbon strategy for increasing the competitiveness of the economy¹⁵

The creation of a climate favorable for the development of entrepreneurship is important for increasing the competitiveness of the national economy, which is the fourth direction of the Lisbon program. To achieve these goals, EU experts propose focusing efforts on the following priority areas:

- encouraging the population to open new businesses;
- improve the education system in such a way as to instill entrepreneurship skills already at the initial stages of education;

- create conditions for the development of entrepreneurship by minimizing the risks of bankruptcy;
- develop preferential business financing schemes;
- improve the legislative framework and reduce administrative barriers.

The next important direction of the Lisbon program is the implementation of social policy with an emphasis on economic growth, one of the main components of which is employment policy aimed at maintaining economic stability and improving public finances in the long term. The program sets as a key

¹³Systematized by the author.

¹⁴White Paper on Science and Technology 2017, p. 46.

¹⁵Compiled by the author. Source: Zuev V.V. Competitiveness program <https://www.hse.ru/data/391/480/1238/Zuev.pdf>

goal the achievement of 80% employment of the working population by 2025. Particular attention in the Lisbon Strategy is paid to the connection between the education and qualifications of the workforce and the competitiveness of manufactured products. In Uzbekistan, “providing the population with new jobs and a guaranteed source of income, decent working condi-

tions” is also identified as priority areas of state policy¹⁶.

The experience of the Russian Federation in increasing the competitiveness of products, firms, industries and the economy as a whole deserves attention. Russian scientists have developed the following structure of a comprehensive competitive strategy, which consists of several areas:

Pic. 7. Main directions of a comprehensive competitive strategy¹⁷

In achieving each of the directions, scientists identify a number of goals, in particular, for the first of them, the most important are increasing the level of liberalization of the economy, the efficiency of government agencies, increasing the participation of the credit and banking system in financing innovative processes, rationalizing the structure of the economy with an emphasis on the development of small and medium-sized companies, as well as clusters. In the second direction, it is advisable to comprehensively stimulate foreign investors, which is designed to attract advanced technologies to the country. In the third direction, the creation of close interaction between science and production, the formation of a single information space for the exchange of knowledge and ideas between participants in the innovation process, and the introduction of mechanisms for the protection of intellectual property are important. The fourth direction involves the formation of an effective regulatory framework and infrastructure for the development of information and communication technologies, designed to increase the efficiency of their use both at the level of government bodies and the population, as well as business structures. In the last, fifth direction, it is important to increase the level of education and professional training of personnel, for which it is advisable to strengthen the educational potential in the country, including and even primarily in the field of information and communication technologies.

Research by Kazakh experts led to the conclusion that in order to increase the competitiveness of companies, which is intended to increase the competitiveness of the national economy as a whole, it is necessary to stimulate an increase in the share of expenses allocated to personnel training, to increase corporate income tax rates using an increasing coefficient to deduct expenses for personnel training and payment labor, introduce mandatory payment for industrial practice by educational institutions, rehabilitate the banks' loan portfolio, which will reduce the cost of financing and increase its terms¹⁸.

Analysis of the research. As priority tasks of the Strategy for Building a New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. The government of the republic has set the goal of implementing the idea “New Uzbekistan - a country of competitive products”, including through an open competitive selection of 200 companies to provide comprehensive support in transforming them into the country's leading exporters¹⁹. The annual global study and its accompanying ranking of countries around the world in terms of economic competitiveness evaluates four main indicators of key aspects of a country's economic life: the state of the economy, the effectiveness of government, the state of the business environment, and the state of infrastructure. Uzbekistan does not participate in the GCI ranking (Tab.4).

¹⁶ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-60 dated January 28, 2022 “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.” <https://nrm.uz/>

¹⁷ Smirnova E. S. Foreign experience in increasing competitiveness and the possibility of its use in Russian conditions // Modern competition. 2010. No. 6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/>

¹⁸ According to the information and analytical website <https://inbusiness.kz/ru/>

¹⁹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-60 dated January 28, 2022 “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.” <https://nrm.uz/>

Table 4

Top 20 in the ranking of countries in the world by global competitiveness (GCI), 2021-2022²⁰

2022	A country	2021	↑↓
1	Switzerland	3	+2
2	Sweden	6	+4
3	Denmark	2	-1
4	Netherlands	4	-
5	Singapore	1	-4
6	Norway	7	+1
7	Hong Kong	5	-2
8	Taiwan	eleven	+3
9	United Arab Emirates	9	-
10	USA	10	-
11	Finland	13	+2
12	Luxembourg	15	+3
13	Ireland	12	-1
14	Canada	8	-6
15	Germany	17	+2
16	China	20	+4
17	Qatar	14	-3
18	Great Britain	19	+1
19	Austria	16	-3
20	New Zealand	22	+2

However, what is progressive is the fact that in the ranking of industrial competitiveness, Uzbekistan took eleventh place among twenty-two countries of Central and Western Asia, moving up two lines, as well as fifth place among the CIS countries (Tab.5).

Table 5

Industrial competitiveness index in 2021-2022²¹

No.	A country	2022		2021		↑↓
		place	point	place	point	
1.	Russia	35	0.096	34	0.097	-1
2.	Belarus	46	0.064	47	0.063	+1
3.	Kazakhstan	65	0.038	65	0.035	-
4.	Ukraine	69	0.035	69	0.035	-
5.	Uzbekistan	94	0.017	95	0.016	+1
6.	Armenia	99	0.015	103	0.012	+4
7.	Moldova	108	0.011	111	0.01	+3
8.	Azerbaijan	118	0.009	121	0.008	+3
9.	Kyrgyzstan	123	0.008	124	0.008	-1
10.	Tajikistan	129	0.006	128	0.005	-1

It should be noted that increasing the level of funding for science and scientific development is determined by one of the key tasks of the government of Uzbekistan - in accordance with the Concept for the development of science in the republic, it is planned to increase the share of all funds allocated to science in relation to the gross domestic product: by 2025 by 6 times , by 2030 - 10 times²² (Tab.6).

²⁰Compiled by the author. Source: Institute of Management Development: IMD World Competitiveness Yearbook 2021.<https://gtmarket.ru/ratings/imd-world-competitiveness-ranking>

²¹Compiled by the author. Source: data<https://stat.unido.org/cip/>

²²Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-6097 dated October 29, 2020 "On approval of the concept of science development until 2030"<https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5073449>

Table 6

Experience of foreign countries in increasing the competitiveness of companies²³

State	Issues identified	Solutions
USA	Research has found that increased concentration, firstly, impedes innovation, and secondly, that it leads to significant concentration in the labor market and leads to lower wages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - creation of structures and mechanisms that focus on highly qualified personnel capable of increasing the competitiveness of companies; - unity of scientific, technical and tax policies; - use of various forms of public-private partnership
China	The structure of the economy is far from perfect, the focus of enterprises only on external sales, the insufficient efficiency of manufacturing enterprises, especially state-owned ones, the ineffective distribution of production capacity in key industries, as well as the relatively low level of quality of goods in general	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ensuring the country's technological independence (transition from importing technology to the formation and development of its own innovative potential); - creation of a SEZ (orientation towards the formation and development of export-oriented production); - widespread use of foreign capital (construction and operation of infrastructure facilities); - institutionalization of state support for business (development of processes of regionalization and decentralization of state powers and strengthening the financial base of local authorities)
Japan	The problem of the need to create a mechanism for the transfer of research results (including fundamental ones) conducted in the universities themselves into the real economy. According to the Japanese National Institute of Science and Technology Policy, on average only 5% of companies use university developments and technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high quality of products due to the use of an effective quality management system and the use of highly qualified workers; - making major investments in new technologies and rapid deployment of new products; - trans nationalization of Japanese financial and industrial corporations and their transformation into large international financial centers - White Paper on Science and Technology, one of the goals of which is to address issues of increasing the competitiveness of companies

Further analyzed the level of R&D spending in some countries around the world during 2016-2021 as a percentage of GDP.

Table 7

Level of R&D spending in some countries around the world in 2016-2021, as a percentage of GDP²⁴

A country	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
South Korea	4.15	4.29	4.22	4.23	4.55	4.81
Israel	4.09	4.17	4.26	4.51	4.82	4.95
Japan	3.31	3.40	3.28	3.16	3.21	3.26
Sweden	3.30	3.14	3.26	3.27	3.40	3.34
Finland	3.29	3.17	2.89	2.74	2.76	2.77
Austria	2.95	3.08	3.05	3.13	3.05	3.17
Germany	2.82	2.87	2.91	2.92	3.04	3.09
USA	2.71	2.72	2.72	2.76	2.82	2.84
Belgium	2.33	2.39	2.46	2.56	2.70	2.82
France	2.24	2.28	2.27	2.22	2.21	2.20
Great Britain	1.64	1.66	1.67	1.68	1.70	1.72
Russia	1.03	1.07	1.10	1.10	1.11	0.99
Uzbekistan	0.20	0.16	0.17	0.18	0.16	0.13
Tajikistan	0.12	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.10

However, in practice, we see Uzbekistan significantly lagging behind many countries of the world.

Result of the research. Analysis of the essence of competitiveness allows us to conclude that its growth is a vital condition for the development of the national economy, since it allows increasing production capac-

ity, enhancing export potential, reducing unemployment and ensuring economic growth, which is ultimately intended to improve the standard of living of the population. The competitiveness of products, companies and industries determines the state of the national economy as a whole.

The assessment of competitiveness is important,

²³Systematized by the author.

²⁴UNESCO Institute for Statistics: Research and Development Expenditure 2021. <https://gtmarket.ru/ratings/research-and-development-expenditure>

since on the basis of it is possible to attract investors, partners for joint activities, and government agencies can build policies in relation to a particular enterprise. To determine the level of competitiveness of an enterprise, it is necessary to calculate and analyze indicators characterizing the activities of the enterprise in specific market conditions. The set of indicators may vary depending on the specifics of the enterprise's activities, its life cycle, external conditions, government policy, etc.

Thus, the positive aspects that we noted in foreign practice of increasing the competitiveness of products, companies, industries and the economy as a whole is the fact that in economically developed countries effective regulations are adopted aimed at promoting competition in the economy, a well-thought-out tax policy is being implemented to stimulate the development of competition, various forms of public-private partnerships are being used, the authorities are providing comprehensive assistance to the development of entrepreneurship and small businesses, and that policies are being implemented, aimed at transitioning from the import of technology to the formation and development of its own innovative potential, the widespread use of foreign capital, the development of information and communication technologies, increasing the level of education and professional skills, which determines the quality of labor resources. All of the above measures contribute to ensuring the growth of competitive advantages of companies, markets and the national economy.

Conclusion. Based on the foregoing, we can conclude that in conditions of profound structural changes in the international and national markets, the main task of the enterprise is to find its niche in a competitive market. To do this, the enterprise must take into account the characteristics of the modern market. The factors that increase the competitiveness of an enterprise come first: the competitiveness of the product, the financial condition of the enterprise, the effectiveness of marketing activities, profitability of sales, image, management efficiency. Maintaining a high level of competitiveness is ensured by all components of the marketing means available to the enterprise. The production and effective sale of competitive goods and services is a general indicator of the viability of an enterprise, its ability to effectively use its production, scientific, technical, labor, and financial potential.

References

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026." <https://nrm.uz/>

2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-6097 dated October 29, 2020 "On approval of the concept of science development until 2030" <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5073449>

3. Benderskaya E.A. Stages of the evolution of competitive advantages // Electronic scientific publication "Scientific Notes of Tomsk State University" 2014, Volume 5, No. 4, pp. 1201-1205 https://pnu.edu.ru/media/ejournal/articles-2014/TGU_5_343.pdf

4. Zuev V.V. Competitiveness program <https://www.hse.ru/data/391/480/1238/Zuev.pdf>

5. Karlof B. Business strategy [Text]: concept, content, symbols: trans. from English / B. Karlof; ed. E. V. Vinogradova. M.: Economics, 1991. 239 p.

6. Porter M. International competition: Competitive advantages of countries. Per. from English edited by Shchetinina V.D. // M. International relations, 1993. 896 p.

7. Risin S.I. Foreign experience of public administration in increasing the competitiveness of the region // Modern competition. 2009. No. 2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/>

8. Safiullin N.Z., Safiullin L.N. Managing the competitiveness of enterprises // Monograph. - Kazan: Publishing house Kazansk. University, 2008. - 189 p.

9. Smirnova E. S. Foreign experience in increasing competitiveness and the possibility of its use in Russian conditions // Modern competition. 2010. No. 6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/>

10. Smith A. An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations. Books 1-3. M.: Direct-Media. 2014. - 442 p. Ricardo D. The beginnings of political economy and taxation. M.: 2016. - 234 p. Say J.B. Treatise on Political Economy. Frederic Bastiat Economic sophisms. Economic harmonies - M.: Delo, 2000. - 232 p.

11. Fatkhutdinov R.A. The essence of competitiveness // Modern competition. 2009. No. 3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/>

12. Shvets I.Yu. Classification of competitive advantages and factors of various objects // Economics and Management No. 4 - 2011 <http://kafmen.ru/>

13. UNESCO Institute for Statistics: Research and Development Expenditure 2021. <https://gtmarket.ru/ratings/research-and-development-expenditure>

14. White Paper on Science and Technology 2017, p. 46.

Internet sites:

<https://inbusiness.kz/ru/>
<https://stat.unido.org/cip/>
<https://gtmarket.ru/ratings/imd-world-competitiveness-ranking>
<https://www.hse.ru/data/391/480/1238/Zuev.pdf>